

DESIGN OF GFRP-RC COLUMNS WITH THE NEW ACI 440.11-22 CODE

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ABSTRACT

The American Concrete Institute has recently codified requirements for design of concrete structures reinforced with GFRP bars. ACI Code 440.11-22 is written in mandatory language that can be adopted by building codes or referenced by licensed design professionals and building officials. Design of GFRP-RC members follows the basic design philosophy from steel-RC, modified to account for both the lower stiffness and absence of yield in GFRP bars. This paper discusses design of GFRP-RC columns, highlighting differences from what is encountered in design of steel-RC columns and identifying design issues that may result when implementing the new GFRP-RC Code requirements.

KEYWORDS

Case studies, Codes, GFRP, columns, reinforced concrete.

INTRODUCTION

Steel reinforcement has been used in many concrete and masonry structures since the middle of the 19th century. Many older concrete structures would not still be standing today, if it were not for the implementation of steel reinforcement. However, even though steel reinforcement is reliable, under certain environments such as exposure to saltwater or de-icing salts or where electromagnetic transparency is required, a better option might be the use of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) reinforcement. FRP bars have been implemented in reinforced concrete (RC) for several decades in structures such as bridge decks, roadways, substation pads, chemical plants, hospital MRI rooms, sea walls and other marine structures.

The American Concrete Institute (ACI) has published ACI CODE-440.11-22 [ACI 2022], herein referred to as the “GFRP Code,” as a standardized document to be implemented in building codes in a similar manner as the ACI 318 Code for steel reinforcement. Design recommendations for FRP-RC that were published by ACI prior to the GFRP Code, such as Guide for the Design and Construction of Concrete Reinforced with FRP Bars [ACI 2015], were only meant as a means to aid design professionals and building officials in the design of FRP-RC structures. However, in the United States, the GFRP Code can now be adopted by a jurisdiction’s prevailing building code or by reference through a model building code. This paper discusses column design in a mid-rise RC building, which was first designed with steel reinforcement using the ACI 318 Code [ACI 2019], and then re-designed with GFRP reinforcement using the GFRP Code.

COLUMN DESIGN FORCES

An interior column of a symmetric G+3 building at the ground-floor level was analyzed and designed twice, first with steel and then with GFRP reinforcement. The structural system is an ordinary concrete moment frame, with six (6) 11 m bays in the main direction and five (5) 4.3 m bays in the perpendicular direction; story height is 3.6 m and the frame is classified as “sway” so the limits on slenderness ratio for a short column classification are 22 with steel reinforcement and 17 with GFRP reinforcement. The column’s factored forces and moments from a first-order elastic analysis using ETABS commercial software are shown in Table 1. Two common controlling load combinations were considered: (i) $1.2D+1.6L+0.5S$ and (ii) $1.2D+1.0L+1.0W+0.5S$. Because the lateral force resisting systems are symmetrical, an interior lower-level column will likely be controlled by one of the load combinations from Table 1. Initial column cross-sectional dimensions of 380 mm x 380 mm were determined by assuming an average compressive stress of $0.5f_c'$ to carry the 2286 kN maximum factored axial load from load combination (i) in Table 1.

Table 1: Factored forces and first-order moments acting on interior column between Levels 1 and 2

Loads considered	Dead + live + snow	Dead + wind + live + snow	
Factored Load Combination	i) $U = 1.2D + 1.6L + 0.5S$	ii) $U = 1.2D + 1.0W + 1.0L + 0.5S$	
Load Breakout	$1.2D + 1.6L + 0.5S$	$1.2D + 1.0L + 0.5S$	$1.0W$
V_u (kN)	0	0	22.9
P_u (kN)	2286	2015	0
$(M_u)_{top}$ (kN-m)	1.8	1.6	± 43.8
$(M_u)_{bot}$ (kN-m)	-1.2	-1.0	± 23.8

The column is classified as long using both steel and GFRP reinforcement. Although the 380 mm x 380 mm cross section satisfies all requirements if the column is reinforced with 1% Grade 60 steel ($E_s = 200$ GPa, $f_y = 414$ MPa), analysis showed that the same size cross section becomes too slender if reinforced with GFRP bars that have a tensile modulus $E_f = 45$ GPa. Thus, the column cross section was increased slightly to 405 mm x 405 mm for the GFRP-RC column, reducing the moment magnification factor for PA (lateral drift) effects determined by hand calculations from 1.13 for the 380 mm x 380 mm column with steel reinforcement to 1.10 for the 405 mm x 405 mm column with GFRP reinforcement. The design forces for the GFRP-RC column based on slenderness effects at the column ends are $P_u = 2015$ kN and the larger magnified design end moment $M_u = M_{2ns} + \delta_s M_{2s} = 1.6 + 1.10(43.8) = 48.2$ kN-m from load combination (ii) in Table 1. However, checking second-order $P\delta$ effects along the column length, based on minimum eccentricity of $15 + 0.03h = 27$ mm, results in a larger moment $M_c = \delta M_{2min} = 1.11(2015 \text{ kN})(0.027 \text{ m}) = 60.4$ kN-m along the column length than at either member end. Thus, the column must be designed to support 2015 kN of factored axial load along with a magnified factored moment of 60.4 kN-m from load combination (ii), as well as 2286 kN factored axial load and 1.8 kN-m bending moment (the gravity moment did not require moment magnification and is small enough to be neglected) from gravity load combination (i). Details are provided in Midrar [2023].

DESIGN OF GFRP-RC COLUMN

Definition of Material Properties

The design of columns is often an iterative process. The design presented here uses normalweight concrete with a 35 MPa specified 28-day compressive strength ($E_c = 28$ GPa). The final design for the GFRP reinforcement consists of M19 longitudinal bars and M9 transverse ties that meet the minimum requirements from ASTM D7957 [2022]. GFRP bar tensile strength decreases with increasing diameter, due to the mechanics of shear transfer between the glass fibers. The guaranteed tensile strength (defined in ASTM D7957 to be the value reported by the manufacturer as no larger than the mean strength minus 3 standard deviations) must be at least 831 MPa for M9 and 641 MPa for M19 GFRP bars, respectively, based on nominal cross-sectional dimensions. The GFRP Code applies an environmental reduction factor $C_E = 0.85$ to the guaranteed strength to determine the design tensile strength $f_{fu} = 706$ MPa for M9 and 545 MPa for M19 GFRP bars, respectively. ASTM D7957 specifies that GFRP bars' average tensile modulus of elasticity must be at least 44.8 GPa. Current generation GFRP bars can have tensile moduli closer to 60 GPa; however, in this study a 45 GPa minimum value was assumed. Strength of a GFRP bar at a bend is less than the strength of the straight portion of the bar; here, the design strength of the bent portion of the bar f_{fb} is assumed to be 60% of the straight bar design strength, as permitted by the GFRP Code and ASTM D7957. However, the GFRP Code also limits the design tensile strength of transverse reinforcement to the smaller of f_{fb} and $0.005E_f$; in this case with lower modulus GFRP bars, the M9 ties are limited to a 225 MPa design tensile strength, which is considerably smaller than the 424 MPa bent bar design tensile strength.

As GFRP bars are linear elastic to failure, the design tensile strain is $\epsilon_{fu} = f_{fu}/E_f = 545 \text{ MPa}/45,000 \text{ MPa} = 0.0121$ for the M19 straight GFRP bars used as longitudinal reinforcement. However, Section 10.3.2.1 of ACI Code 440.11 limits the design tensile strain of the GFRP bars to not more than 0.01 if the factored axial load is greater than $0.1f_c'A_g$ in compression. For our column, $0.1f_c'A_g = 0.1(35 \text{ MPa})(405 \text{ mm})^2 = 574$ kN, which is less than the factored axial compression loads from Table 1; thus, we limit the design tensile strain for the M19 longitudinal bars to 0.01 (and the corresponding design tensile

strength f_{fd} to 45,000 MPa (0.01) = 450 MPa in place of $f_{fu} = 545$ MPa) for those combinations of factored axial force and moment on the interaction diagram that include axial compression, P_u , of at least 574 kN.

Construction of Interaction Diagram and Selection of Longitudinal Reinforcement

Section 22.4 of ACI Code 440.11 covers provisions for the calculation of P_n and M_n and references Section 22.2 for strain limits. The column geometry and reinforcement are determined according to the factored axial load and second-order moments found by moment magnification.

The interaction of P_n and M_n is evaluated by constructing an interaction diagram. A spreadsheet was developed to construct the interaction diagram for any square column cross section and reinforcement ratio, ρ . The spreadsheet analyzes square columns for combined axial and flexural strength. The user inputs the column dimensions, compressive strength of concrete, reinforcement ratio and size of the preferred longitudinal bars. The spreadsheet places the first and last bar layers as close to the column faces as permitted (allowing for concrete cover plus tie bar size). The remaining layers are evenly spaced between the outer layers. The spacing of the bars within each layer is similar to the placement of the layers. The first and last bar are as close to the outer face as permitted and the remaining bars are evenly spaced between the outer bars, as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Column cross section

The design moments in this column are not large, even after moment magnification, so we begin with the minimum area of reinforcement $A_{s,min} = 0.01A_g = 0.01 \times 405^2 = 1640 \text{ mm}^2$ and assume a uniform distribution of bars around the perimeter. At least four bars are needed in a rectangular column. We have chosen to use eight bars, with one in each corner and one at the midpoint of each side (3 layers: 3 bars, 2 bars, 3 bars) as shown in Fig. 1. This corresponds to a required bar area of $1640 \text{ mm}^2 / 8 = 205 \text{ mm}^2$ so M19 GFRP bars ($A_b = 284 \text{ mm}^2$) are chosen for the longitudinal reinforcement, resulting in a 1.4% column reinforcement ratio. Although the GFRP Code permits reinforcement ratios between 1% and 8%, the longitudinal reinforcement in columns is typically limited to 4% to accommodate lap splice zones that will have twice as much reinforcement in the common situation where all lap splices occur at the same location.

The spreadsheet does a sectional strength analysis using an equivalent rectangular stress distribution according to Section 22.2.2.4 in ACI Code 440.11. As per Section 22.2.3.3 in ACI Code 440.11, GFRP reinforcement in the compression zone is treated as having the same strength and stiffness as the surrounding concrete, a significant difference from how steel reinforcement is handled. GFRP's anisotropic and nonhomogenous behaviour complicates testing in compression, but its compressive modulus of elasticity has been shown to be comparable to its tensile modulus [Deitz et al. 2003]. Because the axial stiffness of GFRP in compression is comparable to that of concrete (the modular ratio in this example is $45 \text{ GPa} / 28 \text{ GPa} = 1.6$), the assumption that the GFRP bars in the compression zone can be replaced with an equal area of compression concrete is reasonably conservative.

M9 ties are provided as the minimum permitted bar diameter per Section 25.7.2.2 in ACI Code 440.11. Unlike steel reinforcing bars where concrete cover and durability are related, the concrete cover provisions for GFRP bars are related only to constructability, bond, and fire-related performance issues. The minimum cover is provided in Section 20.6 of ACI Code 440.11. The spreadsheet calculates the

distances to the layers of reinforcement, which is needed for later calculations, by using the tie bar size, cover to tie, and longitudinal bar size, as shown in Table 2.

Note that the range of measured cross-sectional areas as permitted by ASTM D7957 – and thus the range of measured bar diameters – is larger for GFRP bars than what is typical for steel bars, which can impact on constructability issues such as how many GFRP bars can fit in a given width and meet minimum clear bar spacing requirements.

Table 2: Number of bars per layer

Layer	d_i (mm)	No. long. bars	A_f (mm ²)
0	75	3	850
1	202.5	2	568
2	330	3	850
Total		8	2268

The interaction diagram is constructed by using basic principles of equilibrium and strain compatibility to calculate combinations of P_n and M_n that result when the concrete strain on the outer compressive edge of the cross section is equal to the 0.003 specified crushing strain, as incremental changes in the values of strain at the farthest layer of longitudinal reinforcement are considered. A number of different cases occur, related to the distance c from the cross section's compressive edge to the location of its neutral axis; for situations in which some of the GFRP bars are located on the compressive side of the cross section, those compression bars are replaced with an equal area of concrete.

Case 1: Pure Compression ($c = +\infty$)

In this condition, we determine the nominal axial compressive capacity of the column with zero eccentricity and under uniform crushing strain. As the entire cross section is in compression, the contribution of all GFRP reinforcement is neglected and replaced with an equivalent area of concrete, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Pure Compression

As per Table 22.4.2.1 in ACI Code 440.11, the axial strength of a section in pure compression is limited to 80% of the nominal axial strength if ties are used as transverse reinforcement, to allow for accidental eccentricities. Maximum nominal axial load is shown in Eq. 1. A 0.65 strength reduction factor is applied to determine the design strength in Eq. 2, as compression-controlled failure governs.

$$P_{n,max} = 0.8P_0 = 0.8(0.85f'_c A_g) = 0.8(0.85)(35 \text{ MPa})(405 \text{ mm})^2 = 3900 \text{ kN} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$\phi P_n = 0.65 \times 3900 = 2535 \text{ kN} \text{ and } \phi M_n = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Case 2: Neutral axis intersecting the bottom fiber ($c = h$)

The strain and stress distributions for this condition are shown in Fig. 3. The concrete stress distribution, $\sigma_c(x)$, is approximated by the Whitney stress block. The contribution of the GFRP reinforcement is still replaced by an equal area of concrete because the entire section is under compression.

Fig. 3: Neutral axis at the lowest level of fibers

The combined nominal axial and moment capacities, P_n and M_n , for 34.5 MPa concrete ($\beta_1 = 0.8$) are given in Eqs. 3a and 3b.

$$P_n = 0.85 f'_c b (\beta_1 c) = 0.85(35)(405)(0.8 \times 405) = 3900 \text{ kN} \quad \text{Eq. 3a}$$

$$\begin{aligned} M_n &= 0.85 f'_c b (\beta_1 c) \left(\frac{h}{2} - \frac{\beta_1 c}{2} \right) \\ &= 0.85(35)(405)(0.8 \times 405) \left(\frac{405}{2} - \frac{0.8 \times 405}{2} \right) = 158 \text{ kN} - \text{m} \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq. 3b}$$

Compression controlled failure with $\phi = 0.65$ will govern in this case too, as all GFRP reinforcement is in compression. Design forces are given in Eq. 4.

$$\phi P_n = 0.65(3900) = 2535 \text{ kN} \text{ and } \phi M_n = 0.65(158 \text{ kN} - \text{m}) = 103 \text{ kN} - \text{m} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Case 3: Neutral axis depth $h > c > c_{bal}$

The cross-section failure is controlled by concrete crushing when the neutral axis depth is situated below the balanced failure location ($c \geq c_{bal}$). Location of the neutral axis for a balanced failure can be computed as shown in Eq. 5, noting that ε_{ft} is limited to 0.01 because $\phi P_n > 0.1 f'_c A_g$.

$$c_{bal} = \frac{\varepsilon_{cu} \times d_2}{\varepsilon_{ft} + \varepsilon_{cu}} = \frac{0.003(330)}{0.010 + 0.003} = 76 \text{ mm} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

Specific points with the neutral axis between h and c_{bal} are considered one by one to develop the interaction diagram. All use the same formulation for calculation of P_n and M_n based on the stress and strain distributions shown in Fig. 4. Here, bars on the compression side of the cross section are replaced with an equivalent area of concrete but bars on the tension side of the neutral axis contribute to the analysis. As failure is still by concrete crushing, the Whitney stress block can be used to approximate the stress distribution.

Fig. 4: Neutral axis below c_{bal} ($c > c_{bal}$ but less than h)

Strain in GFRP reinforcement is given by Eq. 6 while Eqs. 7 and 8 show the formulation for calculation of axial and flexural strengths.

$$\varepsilon_{fi} = 0 \leq \varepsilon_{cu} \left(\frac{d_i - c}{c} \right) \leq \min(0.01, \frac{f_{fu}}{E_f}) \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

$$P_n = 0.85f'_c b(\beta_1 c) - \sum_{i=0}^n (A_{fi} E_f \varepsilon_{fi}) \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

$$M_n = 0.85f'_c b(\beta_1 c) \left(\frac{h}{2} - \frac{\beta_1 c}{2} \right) + \sum_{i=0}^n (A_{fi} E_f \varepsilon_{fi}) \left(d_i - \frac{h}{2} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

Calculations with the neutral axis $c = 254$ mm from the top are shown to illustrate the procedure. The resulting GFRP strains from Eq. 6 are as follows:

$$\varepsilon_{f0} = 0.003 \left(\frac{75 - 254}{254} \right) = -0.0021 \text{ (compression so replace with equivalent area of concrete)}$$

$$\varepsilon_{f1} = 0.003 \left(\frac{202.5 - 254}{254} \right) = -0.0006 \text{ (compression so replace with equivalent area of concrete)}$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = 0.003 \left(\frac{330 - 254}{254} \right) = 0.0009 \text{ (tension so include)}$$

Axial strength is then calculated from Eq. 7:

$$P_n = (0.85)(35)(405)(0.8 \times 254) - [(850)(45,000)(0.0009)] = 2410 \text{ kN}$$

Flexural strength is based on Eq. 8:

$$M_n = \left[0.85(35)(405)(0.8 \times 254) \left(\frac{405}{2} - \frac{0.8 \times 254}{2} \right) \right] + \left[(850)(45,000)(0.0009) \left(330 - \frac{405}{2} \right) \right] \\ = 251 \text{ kN} - m$$

Compression controlled failure with $\phi = 0.65$ will again govern in this condition because the tensile strain in the outermost layer of GFRP $\varepsilon_{fi} = 0.0009$ is less than $0.8 \varepsilon_{fu} = 0.8(0.01) = 0.008$ (note the use of the 1% design tensile strain limit), resulting in the design strengths shown in Eq. 9.

$$\phi P_n = 0.65(2410) = 1566 \text{ kN} \text{ and } \phi M_n = 0.65(251) = 163 \text{ kN} - m \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

Case 4: Balanced conditions ($c = c_{bal}$)

As calculated previously with GFRP tensile strain limited to 0.01, we determined $c_{bal} = 76$ mm. At balanced conditions, GFRP ruptures simultaneously with concrete crushing, so $\varepsilon_{cu} = 0.003$ when $\varepsilon_{ft} = \min(0.01, \frac{f_{fu}}{E_f})$. P_n and M_n are calculated similarly to the formulation for Condition 3; however, in this example the axial force is less than $0.1f'_c A_g$ at balanced conditions, so the full 0.0121 tensile rupture strain is used.

GFRP strains from Eq. 6 become:

$$\varepsilon_{f2} = \varepsilon_{fu} = 0.0121 \text{ (tension so included) with corresponding } c_{bal} = \frac{0.003}{0.0121 + 0.003} (330) = 65 \text{ mm}$$

$$\varepsilon_{f1} = 0.003 \left(\frac{202.5 - 65}{65} \right) = 0.0063 \text{ (tension so included)}$$

$$\varepsilon_{f0} = 0.003 \left(\frac{75 - 65}{65} \right) = 0.0005 \text{ (tension so included)}$$

Axial force from Eq. 7 is then:

$$P_n = 0.85(35)(405)(0.8 \times 65) - [(850(45,000)(0.0121) + (568(45,000)(0.0063) + (850(45,000)(0.0005))] = -16.4 \text{ kN}$$

In this example, at balanced conditions we get axial tension which is different than what would be expected in a steel-RC column. Here, the GFRP bars provide more tension than the concrete provides compression, which means that the balanced condition occurs with axial tension on the cross section. That is not something that is likely to occur when steel reinforcement is used because the steel reinforcement on the compression side of the cross section contributes significantly to the total compression. This behavior has been observed by other researchers [Jawaheri Zadeh and Nanni 2013], when GFRP reinforcement is used because the GFRP bars on the compression side do not contribute to the total compression in the same manner that steel bars do.

Flexural strength is once again based on Eq. 8:

$$M_n = 0.85(35)(405)(0.8 \times 65) \left(\frac{405}{2} - \frac{0.8 \times 65}{2} \right) + \left[\left(850(45,000)(0.0121) \left(330 - \frac{405}{2} \right) \right) + \left(568(45,000)(0.0063) \left(202.5 - \frac{405}{2} \right) \right) + \left(850(45,000)(0.0005) \left(75 - \frac{405}{2} \right) \right) \right] = 167 \text{ kN} - m$$

Tension-controlled failure will govern in this condition, so the strength reduction factor $\phi = 0.55$ as shown in Eq. 10:

$$\phi P_n = 0.55(-16.4) = -9.0 \text{ kN tension} \text{ and } \phi M_n = 0.55(167) = 91.9 \text{ kN} - m \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

Case 5: Neutral axis at the level of the highest section fibers ($c = 0$)

As Fig. 5 shows, there will not be any contribution from concrete as the entire cross section is under tension and the capacity entirely depends upon the GFRP bars in tension. Failure occurs when the bars in the lowest layer reach the rupture strain. Tension-controlled failure will govern in this condition also, with $\phi = 0.55$. Calculations are shown in Eqs. 11-13.

Fig. 5: Neutral Axis Depth $c = 0$

$$P_n = \sum_{i=0}^n (A_{fi} E_f \varepsilon_{fi}) = 850(45,000)(0.0121) + 568(45,000) \left(\frac{202.5}{330} \right) (0.0121) + 850(45,000) \left(\frac{75}{330} \right) (0.0121) = 757 \text{ kN tension} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

$$M_n = \sum_{i=0}^n (A_{fi} E_f \varepsilon_{fi}) \left(d_i - \frac{h}{2} \right) = 850(45,000)(0.0121) \left(330 - \frac{405}{2} \right) + 568(45,000) \left(\frac{202.5}{330} \right) (0.0121) \left(202.5 - \frac{405}{2} \right) + 850(45,000) \left(\frac{75}{330} \right) (0.0121) \left(75 - \frac{405}{2} \right) = 45.6 \text{ kN} - m \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

$$\phi P_n = 0.55(757) = 416 \text{ kN tension and } \phi M_n = 0.55(45.6) = 25.1 \text{ kN} - m \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

Case 6: Pure Tension ($c = -\infty$)

The case of pure tension results from uniform tensile strain over the entire cross section as shown in Fig. 6. The maximum tensile force constitutes the lowermost point of any interaction diagram and is the other point (in addition to pure compression) that corresponds to zero eccentricity. Due to the linear behavior of the reinforcement, the portion of the interaction curve from the point of $c = 0$ to the point of $c = -\infty$ is linear.

Fig. 6: Pure Tension

The nominal axial tension capacity, P_n , is given in Eq. 14, while Eq. 15 shows the design strengths using $\phi = 0.55$ for a tension-controlled failure.

$$P_n = \sum_{i=0}^n (A_{fi} E_f \varepsilon_{fu}) = [(850(45,000)0.0121) + (568(45,000)0.0121) + (850(45,000)0.0121)] = 1235 \text{ kN tension} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

$$\phi P_n = 0.55(1235) = 679 \text{ kN tension and } \phi M_n = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

Case 7: Pure Moment ($P_n = 0$)

To find flexural capacity of the column without axial load, nominal moment capacity is calculated by treating the column as a beam with GFRP reinforcement in several layers under governing tension-controlled failure conditions. In this condition, axial capacity of the column will be 0 and flexural capacity is calculated as given in Eq. 16. Depth of stress block ' a ' is conservatively assumed equal to $\beta_1 c_{bal}$, but here $c_{bal} = 65$ mm as previously calculated based on the 0.0121 GFRP rupture strain, as there is no factored axial compression acting with the bending moment.

$$M_n = \sum_{i=0}^n (A_{fi} E_f \varepsilon_{fi}) \left(d_i - \frac{\beta_1 c_{bal}}{2} \right) = \left[(850(45,000)0.0121) \left(330 - \frac{0.8(65)}{2} \right) \right] + \left[\left(568(45,000) \left(\frac{202.5-65}{330-65} \right) 0.0121 \right) \left(202.5 - \frac{0.8(65)}{2} \right) \right] + \left[\left(850(45,000) \left(\frac{75-65}{330-65} \right) 0.0121 \right) \left(75 - \frac{0.8(65)}{2} \right) \right] = 170 \text{ kN} - m \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

Design strengths are then $\phi P_n = 0$ and $\phi M_n = 0.55(170) = 93.4 \text{ kN} - m$

The complete interaction diagram is shown in Fig. 7. Note that the balanced failure case and the pure moment case give very similar values for axial load and moment in this example; such will not always be the case, depending on the column layout. As Fig. 7 shows, both factored load combinations, including the magnified moment from load combination (ii), fall within the safe design envelope of the interaction

diagram. Due to this example's small load eccentricity, both load combinations (gravity only and gravity plus lateral load from wind) that were considered in the design result in all GFRP bars falling on the compression side of the neutral axis. Thus, eight (8) M19 GFRP bars evenly spaced around the perimeter are used as longitudinal reinforcement in the 405 mm x 405 mm column cross section. Had the load eccentricity been larger, we would likely have needed a larger column cross section with some of the GFRP bars in tension under the design loads.

Fig. 7: Interaction Diagram for 405 mm x 405 mm column with 1% GFRP reinforcement

Design of Transverse Reinforcement

From Table 1, Load Combination (ii) has the largest shear demand.

$$V_u = 22.9 \text{ kN} \qquad P_u = 2015 \text{ kN}$$

Using Section 10.6.2.1 from ACI Code 440.11, a minimum area of shear reinforcement $A_{fv,min}$ must be provided in all regions where the factored shear is larger than the value given in Eq. 17. Note that the strength reduction factor $\phi = 0.75$ for shear.

$$V_u > \phi 0.21 k_{cr} \sqrt{f'_c} b_w d = 0.75(0.21)\sqrt{35}(405)(65) = 24.5 \text{ kN} \qquad \text{Eq. 17}$$

Here, k_{cr} should account for the effect of the axial compression to locate the cracked section neutral axis but it is conservative to replace $k_{cr}d$ with 65 mm which is the location of the neutral axis from the pure moment case. As $V_u = 22.9 \text{ kN}$, shear reinforcement is not required in the column.

Using Section 10.7.6.2 in ACI Code 440.11, the requirements for lateral support of GFRP longitudinal bars with transverse ties are as follows:

- a) In any story, the bottom tie shall be located not more than one-half the tie spacing above the top of footing or slab.
- b) In any story, the top tie shall be located not more than one-half the tie spacing below the lowest horizontal reinforcement in the slab, drop panel, or shear cap. If beams or brackets frame into all sides of the column, the top tie shall be located not more than 75 mm below the lowest horizontal reinforcement in the shallowest beam or bracket.

Ties must also meet requirements defined in Section 25.7.2 of ACI Code 440.11. The maximum spacing shall not exceed the least of:

- (a) $12 d_b$ of the longitudinal bar = $12 (19) = 228$ mm
- (b) $24 d_b$ of the transverse bar = $24(9.5) = 228$ mm
- (c) smaller of h or $b = 405$ mm

So we will provide M9 GFRP ties at 225 mm center-to-center spacing. The minimum longitudinal bar spacing is controlled by the largest of $1.5d_b = 1.5(19) = 28.5$ mm, $4/3d_{agg}$ where $d_{agg} = 25$ mm, thus $4/3(25) = 33$ mm or 38 mm, which is easily met in this case. However, designers should note that GFRP bar diameters may be as much as 2 mm larger than the nominal bar diameter and carefully consider the impact on spacing when determining if bars will fit in the cross section.

Section 25.7.2.3 of ACI Code 440.11 also requires ties to meet the following requirements:

- a) Every corner and alternate longitudinal bar shall have lateral support provided by the corner of a tie with an included angle of not more than 135 degrees;
- b) Each bar shall have less than 150 mm clear on each side along the tie from a laterally supported bar;
- c) If ties are constructed from pairs of overlapping U shapes, overlaps at ends of adjacent rectilinear ties shall be staggered around the perimeter.

Ties with 90 degree standard hooks are acceptable for this case, as center-to-center spacing between the longitudinal bars is 125 mm and there are only three bars along each side.

Joint Design Check

The transfer of column axial force through the joint must be checked. It is common to have higher strength concrete in the columns and walls and a lower strength in the floor system which can require additional checks, but this building uses the same concrete strength for both the columns and floor system so no additional calculations or adjustments are necessary.

Sections 15.2.2, 15.2.3, and 15.4 of ACI Code 440.11 require that beam-column joints be designed and detailed for shear if moment is being transferred to the column. Section 15.4 does not require minimum shear reinforcement through the joint, if the joint is restrained in accordance with 15.2.4 or 15.2.5, and is not part of a seismic-force-resisting system. Here, section 15.4.2 applies which requires that minimum shear reinforcement, of at least the greater of Eqs. 18a and b, is provided in the joint region even if minimum shear reinforcement is not required in the column.

$$A_{fv,min} = 0.062\sqrt{f'_c} \frac{b_w}{f_{ft}} s \quad \text{Eq. 18a}$$

$$A_{fv,min} = 0.35 \frac{b_w}{f_{ft}} s \quad \text{Eq. 18b}$$

For each tie, $A_{fv} = 71 \text{ mm}^2 \times 2 \text{ legs} = 142 \text{ mm}^2$. The required spacing is found as the smaller value from Eqs. 18a and b:

$$s = \frac{142(225)}{0.062\sqrt{35}(405)} = 215 \text{ mm}$$

$$s = \frac{142(225)}{0.35(405)} = 225 \text{ mm}$$

The maximum spacing is one-half the depth of the shallowest beam or slab framing into the element and must be distributed along the column for the full depth of the deepest member. This results in the maximum spacing in the joint of $s = \frac{710}{2} = 355$ mm. Thus, two ties are used along the depth of the joint at a spacing of 200 mm to satisfy minimum shear reinforcement through the joint.

Column Splice Detailing and Development Length

It is common to begin lap splices for vertical reinforcement at the floor level. Since all the splices are at one location, a Class B tension lap splice length is provided. The compression lap splice length is considered to be equal to the tension lap length according to Section 25.5.5.1 of ACI Code 440.11. Lap splice length of bars in tension are given in Section 25.5.5.2 as the greater of:

- (a) $\ell_{st} = 1.3\ell_d$ where ℓ_d is determined from Eq. 19
- (b) $\ell_{st} = 20d_b$
- (c) 305 mm

Section 25.4.2.4 of ACI Code 440.11 specifies development length ℓ_d to be the greater of $20d_b$, 305 mm and the value calculated using Eq. 19.

$$\ell_d = \frac{d_b \left(\frac{f_{fr}}{0.083\sqrt{f_c'}} - 340 \right) \psi_t}{13.6 + \frac{c_b}{d_b}} \text{ where } c_b/d_b \leq 3.5 \quad \text{Eq. 19}$$

For our case, the top bar factor $\psi_t = 1.0$, $c_b = 38 + 9.5 + 9.5 = 57$ mm, and $d_b = 19$ mm, so Eq. 19 gives:

$$\ell_d = \frac{19 \left(\frac{136}{0.083\sqrt{35}} - 340 \right) 1.0}{13.6 + \frac{57}{19}} = -72.1 \text{ mm}$$

As a negative value for development length is unacceptable, in this case ℓ_d is based on the larger of $20d_b = 380$ mm and 305 mm. For the Class B splice, the splice length must be the largest of $20d_b = 380$ mm, 305 mm, and 1.3 times the development length given by Eq. 19; thus the M 19 bars' splice length is 380 mm and equal to their development length.

The code requires the first tie starting on any level to be within $s/2$ of the top of the slab. It is good construction practice to start the tie at 50 to 75 mm from the top of the floor (beginning of the column cage) and then proceed with the typical tie spacing.

At the top of the column cage (bottom of the floor above) ties are required through the beam / slab joint if the longitudinal bars are not confined by the concrete on all four sides. In this case, only two beams frame into the joint so the beam depth below the slab does not provide joint confinement. The slab is on all four sides so it provides confinement and ties are not required in this joint region. The code requires the last tie to be within $s/2$ of the lowest horizontal reinforcement in the confined concrete. Again, it is good construction practice to place a tie at 50 to 75 mm below the confining concrete. The top offset bend at the tie can be located just below the slab. A tie should also be provided at the bottom offset bend. This provides two ties in the joint region within the required spacing. The tie requirements are not additive in this case.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The GFRP-RC column design required a 405 mm x 405 mm cross section with eight (8) M19 GFRP bars to resist the factored loads and moments at the minimum 1% reinforcement ratio. Because shear is very low, only the minimum tie area and spacing (M9 ties at 225 mm on center) are required for support of the longitudinal reinforcement. Since considered design forces are from the lowest floor, this column size and reinforcement will work for the remaining floors. A smaller column may work for the upper floors but the cost of a change in formwork may not overcome the cost of the small amount of concrete that is saved. In some cases, the architect may want to save some space on the upper floors and there may be a compromise between functionality and expense. In comparison, the same building designed with steel reinforcement could use 380 mm x 380 mm columns with eight (8) M15 Grade 60 steel longitudinal bars and still satisfy all second-order analysis and design requirements with a 1.1% reinforcement ratio. Transverse reinforcement in the steel-RC column consisted of M9 ties at 300 mm on center, including through the joint. Axial capacity of the GFRP-RC column under full compression

decreases, as the contribution from GFRP reinforcement in compression is the same as if the GFRP were replaced with compression concrete. Increase of the column cross section to 405 mm x 405 mm with GFRP reinforcement from the 380 mm x 380 mm cross section with steel reinforcement resulted in an increase of 12 cubic meters of concrete for all the columns in the building. Had higher-modulus GFRP bars been considered in the design, it is possible that the 380 mm x 380 mm cross section could have been made to work, due to the small eccentricities of the column moments. On the other hand, had load eccentricity been larger, the requirement for a larger column size when using GFRP reinforcement would have been more pronounced as compared to design for the same load combinations with steel reinforcement.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.